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REVIEWING FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION JOURNALS

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Topics: another topic relevant to the conference but not listed above

Keywords: engineering education research, manuscript review, review criteria, engineering education journals

Reviewers are the unsung heroes of any research field, volunteering their time and receiving recognition or acknowledgement only occasionally and anonymously:

“The authors would like to express our sincere gratitude to the three anonymous referees for their suggestions on how to improve the scholarship of this paper.”

Behind the scenes of the review process, in which authors submit their manuscripts to the editors of journals, are reviewers who engage deeply in advising authors on how to improve their manuscripts. It is a process that often involves multiple iterations over many months. A reviewer who is willing and able to write thorough, constructive, and thoughtful comments is an asset for the journals and editors, and by extension for the whole field. A fact that is often overlooked is that without the work of reviewers, there would be no journals and no scholarly field.

It is also true that reviewing can be rewarding. First, reviewers are often authors as well and benefit from having their own manuscripts reviewed. Second, the review process is often intellectually stimulating in and of itself. This stimulus often leads to insights that help in the development of our own research and writing.

This workshop welcomes those who are interested in taking on review assignments, as well as experienced reviewers willing to share their best practices. Our primary purpose is to develop an understanding of the review process and further our skills in the art of reviewing. The aim is to help the engineering education community to develop manuscripts effectively, while minimising unnecessary agony. All actors – authors, editors, and reviewers – need to recognize that we are on the same side, sharing a common interest in taking the quality of manuscripts to a new level that makes us all proud and furthers the field of engineering education.

Participants will also gain inside information on the editorial process of three well-established engineering education journals. The workshop leaders are editors of:

- *European Journal of Engineering Education (SEFI)*
- *Journal of Engineering Education (ASEE)*
- *IEEE Transactions on Education (IEEE)*

Expected outcomes

As a result of the workshop, we will all be able to:

- Describe the role of peer review for a journal and a scholarly field
- Explain different quality criteria for scholarship in engineering education and their application in the peer review process
- Consider how reviews can help editors make fair decisions
- Consider how reviews can support and challenge authors to improve their manuscripts, by expressing critiques/feedback clearly, constructively and respectfully
- Give examples of particular aspects of a manuscript that a review could bring up

Workshop Outline

INTRODUCTIONS

- Participants and workshop leaders [10 minutes]
- About the Journals [15 minutes]
 - where they stand today
 - aims and scope
 - review criteria and review process

GROUP EXERCISE

- Form teams of 4 and make a mini-poster: “Characteristics of helpful reviews” [30 minutes]

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- Vernissage (hanging and sharing of posters)

PLENARY DISCUSSIONS

- Results from group exercise [30 minutes]

FINISH

- Photographing the posters and signing up to volunteer as reviewers for the various journals [5 minutes]